

An assessment of Egypt's external debt sustainability: using the ARIMA model

Mohamed F. Abd El-Aal

Arish University, Department of Economics

Abstract: This paper aims to determine Egypt's ability to pay its debts and service it by predicting the specific indicators of debt sustainability that were developed by the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank in 2018, so the ARIMA model was used to predict these indicators due to its high accuracy in forecasting to determine Strengths and weaknesses in Egypt's ability to pay its debts. We can assess Egypt's position on debt in the period from 2021 to 2030 as follows, the share of external debt in the GDP in this period does not represent any danger, as it is in the stage of weakness, as it did not exceed 35.8% of GDP in 2030, as well as the service of repaying the external debt Of the GDP and government revenues, they were also in the phase of weakness, with rates of 3.37% and 13.7%, respectively, in 2030. However, the main issue was the share of the external debt in the total Egyptian exports, which reached a dangerous level of 262.1%, and the share of the total Egyptian debt in the GDP, which reached 119.4% in 2030. Hence, the repayment of the external debt service does not represent any problem or danger compared to the aggravation of the external debt for Egyptian exports, as well as the aggravation of the total debt volume to the gross domestic product, which exposes the state to the risks of non-payment in the future.

Keywords: External debt, External debt service, total debt, ARIMA model, debt sustainability

1. Introduction:

External debt or borrowing refers to borrowing money from a foreign country or organization. There are numerous ways to explain it. A country's external debt is defined as the amount of money it owes to financial organizations and governments outside of its own country, such as commercial banks and the United States government (Arnone, Bandiera & Presbitero, 2005; Ajayi & Khan, 2000). In most cases, these loans, including interest, must be repaid by the country in the currency of the loan (as a service). Selling and exporting items to the lender's country can help the borrowing country raise the necessary funds (Obadan, 2004). According to Evgin (2000), external borrowing obtains a government's or government institution's fiscal or real income from sources outside the country. Put another way, borrowing money from residents or institutions outside one's residence. In the words of Ucak (2006), "external debt" is defined as "transfer flows that are taken from foreign resources and have booster effects on national income during their payback."

In the 1980s, external debt sustainability became a major topic. These years were dubbed the "foreign debt crisis years" After all, foreign debt crises plagued many developing countries while affluent countries like the united states of America and Germany were continuously running deficits (Ozkan, 2006).

The ability of any country to service its external debt is referred to as "foreign debt sustainability" Foreign debt is considered sustainable if the country's net future foreign profits equal the current value of its foreign debt. As a result, foreign debt is considered sustainable if the country's intertemporal budget constraint can be met (Mohammadi et al., 2007). Certain ratios or indicators can also monitor debt and external debt sustainability. For example, the external debt ratio to GDP is an important metric. Stabilization of the overall external debt to GDP ratio is necessary. To achieve debt sustainability (Keating and Keating, 2003).

Someratios' critical levels determine whether or not the country's external debt is manageable or unmanageable. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank use these ratios to determine external debt sustainability: external debt to GDP and exports, external debt service to export, and revenue. See the thresholds of debt burden according to IMF in the table (1):

Table (1): Thresholds and Benchmarks Under the DSF

degree	external debt in percent of		External Debt service in percent of		total public debt in percent of
	GDP	Exports	Export	Revenue	GDP
Weak	30	140	10	14	35
Medium	40	180	15	18	55
Strong	50	240	21	23	70

Source: IMF database.

2. Literature Review

Classical, Keynesian, and Ricardian schools of macroeconomic theory have produced a substantial body of work on the sustainability of debt–deficit ratios and the function of debt in the economy, all of which are either supported or dismissed by empirical evidence. An overview of the empirical literature is provided in this section:

Barro (1989) used the Ricardian method to analyze budgetary shortfalls. According to the study's empirical findings, Ricardian economics claims that fiscal policy is irrelevant and that any reduction in current taxes will lead to higher future taxation. A further goal of the author's argument is to show that fiscal policy is useless in a budget deficit position. When revenue generation fails, and monetary financing of the deficit is necessary, the deficit scenario becomes relevant. Burney and Ahmad (1988) assessed Pakistan's debt burden, debt service indicators, and solvency using the important interest rate technique. They concluded that Pakistan's long-term debt repayment capacity was not in excellent shape between 1973 and 1987. Debt growth and its sustainability have been explored by Spaventa (1987). The tax burden must be raised above the socially acceptable threshold to sustain the debt expansion.

For Bohn (1995), it doesn't matter how low-interest rates go as long as the government sticks to its intertemporal budget limitations. Primary surpluses have a positive relationship to GDP denominated in debt, which, according to Bohn, shows the long-term viability of the US fiscal approach (1998). According to Blanchard and Perotti (2002), the growth of the US GDP was affected by changes in government spending and taxes. This research finds it interesting that government spending boosts productivity, whereas taxes have the opposite effect. A lot of attention is paid to the issue of debt accumulation and its effect on economic growth in developing countries.

From 1994 to 1997, researchers Tahir and Ahmad (1998), Hasan, Chaudhri, and Ahmad (1999), and Siddiqui and Kazmi (2001) compared Pakistan's external debt burden indicators with those of other developing countries, including those with higher levels of internal debt (HIPC) and countries with lower levels of external debt (SILC). They found that Pakistan was worse than most of these countries.

Chaudhary-Anwar-Tahir (2000) concluded that Pakistan had a stronger financial position than some of the other South Asian countries investigated. Using the Debt Laffer Curve method, the authors analyzed the debt sustainability of Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal, the Maldives, and Bhutan. From 1970–1971 to 1994–1995, the five countries of Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and Nepal all paid their external debt obligations. According to Pasha and Ghaus, the depreciation of the exchange rate, the interest rate–growth rate differential, and the primary balance influence the public debt-to-GDP ratio (2001). Debt-to-GDP ratio changes were also analyzed in terms of their composition. Between 1980 and 1995, Pakistan's government debt-to-GDP grew by 28%, according to the data.

Favero and Giavazzi (2007) examined the relationship between fiscal policy and debt. According to these researchers, economic shocks can erroneously impact debt if not included in the debt response model. There were considerable beneficial reactions to changes within initial debt burdens in primary surpluses identified by Bohn (2007). Debt sustainability evaluation is part of Ejaz and Javid's study (2009). A function for measuring domestic and external debt sustainability in developing nations is proposed in the research. A major part of the research focused on Pakistan. For assessing public debt sustainability, the researchers utilized interest rates, growth differentials, and the primary budget balance level; debt services and the current account balance were used for assessing external debt sustainability. It was found that Pakistan's government debt was unsustainable during the majority of the period between 1971 and 2008, according to a year-by-year examination (Ejaz & Javid, 2011).

Chandia and Javid's (2013) study thoroughly examines the sustainability of the nation's public debt. Through fiscal reaction functions, the study determined Pakistan's debt sustainability. Findings from the research suggested a weak form of sustainability for Pakistan's governmental debt. The primary budget balance is positively correlated with a country's debt ratio. The findings of Bohn (1998) suggested that surpluses react negatively to changes in government spending, which this study has corroborated. Furthermore, the analysis found that the government's revenues and expenditures may be adjusted to make it financially viable.

The various elements contributing to the debt portion of GDP ratio buildup are studied (Chandia & Javid, 2013). To that end, researchers developed a debt dynamics equation. Interest rate growth, foreign exchange impact, and main budget deficit are all considered in the debt dynamics equation when determining a country's debt. According to a study, a strong correlation exists between the country's main budget deficit and excessive domestic and foreign debt buildup. The primary budget deficit in South Asian countries considered in the study results from inefficient government spending.

Draksaite et al. (2015) have attempted to establish several empirical methodologies for examining the long-term sustainability of public debt. In determining the long-term viability of public debt, the study's authors examined each of the variables above in great detail. To determine whether or not the debt is sustainable, it is necessary to consider several criteria. Debt evaluation and risk management, as well as government solvency and borrowing, are among the elements to be considered when assessing the risk associated with government borrowing.

There has been a lot of attention given to government finances and the structure of public debt in work done by Afonso and Jalles in 2017. Thirteen advanced economies were the focus of the research from 1980 to 2012. The author's estimates show that the debt-to-GDP ratios of the nations covered in the study are responsive to main budget surpluses and deficits. Long-term debt held by the central bank and marketable debt share all play an important role in ensuring that the country's debt structure is long-term sustainable. At this time, short-term liabilities and difficulties in raising long-term bonds are detrimental.

Since the beginning of the latest crisis, China's economic performance has deteriorated. So the Chinese government decided to broaden its budgetary policies as a result. Cuestas and Regis (2018) have studied public debt in China; Research shows that china's debt accumulation is not a steady process. According to the most recent data, China's national debt is unsustainable. Until China's economic growth improves, the report predicts a significant rise in public debt.

Analysis of OECD nations' public debt sustainability is presented (Fournier & Fall, 2017). The non-linear reaction of the primary balance to the debt ratio confirms the fiscal fatigue concept. Additionally, the study has determined the OECD debt ceiling. The debt ceiling is influenced by the status of government behavior, economic growth, market conditions, and monetary policy. The analysis found that the high debt ceiling for several OECD countries is around twice the GDP.

Omotor, D. (2021), This research aims to apply the debt sustainability paradigm to the current condition of sovereign debt in ECOWAS member countries using various ratios. The study used Ratios for measuring debt sustainability, such as the present value approach, country-by-country debt policy rankings, and the solvency ratio of external debt. Research shows that most nations in the ECOWAS region are already on an unsustainable debt path, which might lead to capital flight and an uncontrollable spiral of external borrowing.

3. Egypt's external debt situation:

The Egyptian external debt from 2000 to 2015 was largely stable, as its share of the GDP did not exceed 16% of it in the year 2000, then its contributions to the GDP declined until it reached its lowest ratio in 2011 by about 11.9% GDP. Then the size of the debt went

back to a rapid rise since 2012, but it has been a very significant rise since 2016, as it contributed about 20% of the GDP and jumped until it reached 31.5% in 2020 (fig.1).

As for the share of the Egyptian foreign debt in the total value of Egyptian exports, it exceeded 100% of its value in the period from 2000 to 2005, reaching its highest level in this period at 190% of it in 2002 and reaching its lowest level in 2005 at 112.5%. Then the share of the external debt in the total value of exports decreased by less than 100% from 2006 to 2014, when the external debt reached its lowest percentage in 2008 at 63%. Still, at the end of the period, it reached 95% of the value of exports. As for the period from 2015 to 2020, very high levels of the external debt share of the value of Egyptian exports were witnessed, as the share of the external debt reached about 114.7% in 2015, then it reached more than double the percentage in 2020, reaching 274.8%. This is illustrated by the following figure (Fig. 2):

Figure (1): Comparative external debt to GDP

Source: made by the author

Figure (2): Comparative external debt to Export

Source: made by the author

According to the IMF framework, Egypt's debt burden can be judged, show that in the next table:

Table (2): Egypt's debt burden ratios in 2019-2020

year	external debt in percent of		External Debt service in percent of		total public debt in percent of
	GDP	Exports	exports	revenue	GDP
2019	28.9 (weak)	216 (medium)	2.2 (weak)	9.3 (weak)	84 (strong)
2020	31.9 (weak)	274.8 (strong)	2.9 (weak)	-	88 (strong)

Source: made by the author

According to the previous table, depending on the IMF framework, the external debt to GDP and its services didn't represent any risk to Egypt's Economy. But the risks shown in the external debt are more than twice Egypt's export value, and the total public debt is near the value of Egypt's GDP in 2020. This is up to the short-term debt, representing 9.1% of total external debt.

Due to this dilemma, debt ratios will be predicted by the autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model To see the situation in the future.

4. Methodology

Using the IMF and WB-designed debt sustainability framework to evaluate the evolution of the structure of the debt. The ARIMA model, a time series analysis tool, is used to forecast external debt sustainability future values. Python is used to create the ARIMA time series model because of its vast variety of capabilities for primary data analysis. The ARIMA approach has a series of stages to follow:

a- The identification of the model

The ARIMA model can only be used for stationary time series data. So, the first step is to determine whether or not the time series data is stationary before moving on to the next phase. If the data is not stable, the difference and the amount of data that will be stable must be examined.

The best ARIMA model to use:

There will be various ARIMA models based on the outcomes of stationary identification and identification of ACF and PACF. The auto-regressive parameters will be estimated in the next steps.

c- accuracy

The lower value of both the RMSE, MAE, and MAPE And the high value of the coefficient of the determination (R^2) indicate the high accuracy of the model.

d-Forecasting

After the best model is found, accurate forecasting for the future can be done. Forecasting using this method is more accurate in some situations than forecasting using other time series analysis methods.

For the dataset, the time series for debt ratios were chosen from 2000 to 2020, for data collection, from World Bank data (World Development Indicators) and the Central Bank of Egypt (CBE).

5. Results

After processing the data on Python to obtain the accuracy results for prediction to determine the best model of ARIMA and the accuracy one, the next table is getting:

Table (3): ARIMA model accuracy for external debt sustainability factors

variable	RMSE	MAE	MAPE	R2
Exports (0,0,1)	2.42	1.85	0.041	0.87
external debt services (0,1,1)	1.63	0.12	0.19	0.62
external debt services (0,1,1)	15.1	2.8	0.15	0.78
GDP (0,1,1)	11.7	5.8	0.029	0.95
Revenue (0,1,0)	6.6	3.2	0.07	0.65
total debt (0,1,1)	2.8	2.1	0.025	0.71

Source: made by the author. RMSE (Root mean square error), MAE(mean absolute error), MAPE (mean absolute percentage error), and R2 (the coefficient of determination).

The lower value of both the RMSE, MAE, and MAPE And the high value of the coefficient of the determination indicate the high accuracy of the model. After we determine the best and the most accurate model of ARIMA, prediction can be done, see that table 4

Table (4): external debt sustainability ratios prediction at the period of (2021:2030) by the ARIMA model

year	External Debt/GDP(%)	External Debt /Exports (%)	Debt Service /GDP (%)	Debt Service /Revenue (%)	total debt/GDP(%)
2021	32.69	255.70	3.017	12.91	104.60%
2022	33.72	256.47	3.126	13.04	106.3
2023	34.04	257.63	3.158	13.12	107.9
2024	34.37	261.90	3.188	13.19	109.5
2025	34.64	259.08	3.236	13.36	111.2
2026	34.91	259.66	3.263	13.42	112.8
2027	35.19	260.36	3.288	13.48	114.7
2028	35.46	260.88	3.313	13.53	116.1
2029	35.67	261.74	3.354	13.67	117.8
2030	35.89	262.19	3.375	13.71	119.4

Source: made by the author

Concerning the relative weight of the external debt in the total value of the GDP expected from 2021 to 2030, we find that it is in moderate severity; its percentage did not exceed 35.8% of the GDP in 2030. However, this percentage decreased from 2021-2030 compared to 2020. But concerning the relative weight of these debts in the total value of exports, we find that they fall into the stage of strong risk. The external debt exports ratios did not exceed 262% in 2030 of the total value of Egyptian exports. Despite improvement, it is still located in the stage of strong danger.

As for the relative weight of external debt service in terms of GDP, as it was in the previous period from 2000 to 2020 in low-risk stages, we find that it is also still in low-risk stages in the period from 2021 to 2030. It did not exceed 3.37% of the GDP in 2030. As well as the relative weight of debt service from the total value of government revenues also falls in low-risk stages in the period from 2021 to 2030; it did not exceed 13.7%.

The main dilemma lies in the share of total debt in the GDP. After the share of total debt in the value of GDP was 88% in 2020, it increased during the period from 2021 to 2030 to reach its peak in 2030 by about 119.4%, which is a very strong risk level. . This is due to the state's expansion in internal and external debts during the period from 2021 to 2030, although the expected GDP values increased during the same period.

We can summarize the findings in the following ways:

- A. Forecasting using the ARIMA model gave high accuracy for forecasting the variables of GDP, exports, external debt, revenue, and total debt.
- B. Egypt currently has a sustainable external debt service in the forecast decade regarding the share of debt service in both GDP and exports.
- C. The share of external debt in GDP has shifted from a low-risk stage at present to a medium-risk stage in the forecast decade. As for its share of exports, it was in the stage of strong danger at present and in the expected decade, but the situation will worsen in the future.
- D. Concerning the public debt and its share of output, it also remains in strong danger, and the situation will worsen in the future.
- E. So Egypt has sustainability in repaying the external debt service, but in the future, it will face the problem of repaying the debt.

6. Conclusion

Many variables go into economic forecasts, making them incredibly difficult to anticipate. The economy relies heavily on quantitative and programming methods to predict them. The forecasts are subjected to additional practical and theoretical processing to acquire the most relevant and accurate results. It is often important to depend on the predicted values of indicators rather than investigate the causes of their change while making operational decisions. This is the underlying premise of the ARIMA model.

Given the importance of the country's external debt sustainability, it was necessary to predict the specific economic variables. In a first step, the strengths and weaknesses at present were identified for the sustainability of Egypt's external debt and the future from 2021 to 2030. This is to determine the appropriate economic policy to eliminate weaknesses in the future for the Egyptian economy to proceed with the predicament of foreign debt safely. Foreign exchange revenues must be restructured to pay off external and service debt, enhance economic growth, and boost the country's potential export. Egypt needs a plan to boost domestic resource mobilization, which is essential to its future. In addition to tax reform initiatives, public-private collaboration techniques should be included.

Data Availability:

The data used to support the findings of the study can be obtained from the corresponding author upon request.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

References:

1. Afonso, A., & Jalles, J. T. (2017). Euro area time-varying fiscal sustainability. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 22(3), 244-254.
2. Arnone, M., Bandiera, L., & Presbitero, A. F. (2005). External debt sustainability: Theory and empirical evidence. *Catholic University of Piacenza Economics Working Paper*, 33, 1-47.
3. Arslan, Ö., Florackis, C., & Ozkan, A. (2006). The role of cash holdings in reducing investment–cash flow sensitivity: Evidence from a financial crisis period in an emerging market. *Emerging Markets Review*, 7(4), 320-338.
4. Barro, R. J. (1989). The Ricardian approach to budget deficits. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 3(2), 37-54.
5. Blanchard, O., & Perotti, R. (2002). An empirical characterization of the dynamic effects of changes in government spending and taxes on output. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 117(4), 1329-1368.
6. Bohn, H. (1995). The sustainability of budget deficits in a stochastic economy. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 27(1), 257-271.
7. Bohn, H. (1998). The behavior of US public debt and deficits. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 113(3), 949-963.
8. Bohn, H. (2007). Are stationarity and cointegration restrictions really necessary for the intertemporal budget constraint? *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 54(7), 1837-1847.
9. Burney, N. A., & Ahmad, E. (1988). Determinants of debt problem in Pakistan and its debt-servicing capacity [with comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 27(4), 805-818.
10. Chandia, K. E., & Javid, A. Y. (2013). An analysis of debt sustainability in the economy of Pakistan. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 5, 133-142.
11. Chandia, K. E., & Javid, A. Y. (2013). An assessment of the contributing factors in debt and deficit: A comparative analysis of Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh. *Journal of Globalization and Business Management*, 1, 38-53.
12. Chaudhary, M. A., Anwar, S., & Siddiqui, R. (2001). Debt Laffer curve for south Asian countries [with comments]. *The Pakistan development review*, 705-720.

13. Cuestas, J. C., & Regis, P. J. (2018). On the dynamics of sovereign debt in China: Sustainability and structural change. *Economic Modelling*, 68, 356-359.
14. Daunorienė, A., Drakšaitė, A., Snieška, V., & Valodkienė, G. (2015). Evaluating the sustainability of sharing economy business models. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 213, 836-841.
15. Ejaz, K., & Javid, A. Y. (2011). An assessment of debt sustainability in the scenario of Pakistan's debt burden.
16. Favero, C., & Giavazzi, F. (2007). Debt and the effects of fiscal policy.
17. Fournier, J. M., & Fall, F. (2017). Limits to government debt sustainability in OECD countries. *Economic Modelling*, 66, 30-41.
18. Hasan, P., Chaudhri, F. M., & Ahmad, E. (1999). Pakistan's Debt Problem: Its Changing Nature and Growing Gravity [with Comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 38(4), 435-470.
19. Keating, M. O., & Keating, B. P. (2003). Measuring the sustainability of Latin American external debt. *Applied Economics Letters*, 10(6), 359-362.
20. Khan, M. M. S., & Ajayi, M. S. I. (Eds.). (2000). *External debt and capital flight in Sub-Saharan Africa*. International Monetary Fund.
21. Mohammadi, H., Cak, M., & Cak, D. (2007). Capital mobility and foreign debt sustainability: some evidence from Turkey. *Applied Economics*, 39(19), 2441-2449.
22. Obadan, M. I. (2004). *Foreign Capital Flows and External Debt: Perspectives on Nigeria and the LCDs Group*. Broadway Press.
23. Omotor, D. (2021). External debt sustainability in West African countries. *Review of Economics and Political Science*.
24. Pasha, H. A., Ghaus-Pasha, A., & Ismail, Z. H. (2001). Social Development in Pakistan: Annual Review 2000: Towards Poverty Reduction. *OUP Catalogue*.
25. Siddiqui, R., Siddiqui, R., & Kazmi, A. A. (2001). Determinants of Debt Rescheduling in Pakistan [with Comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 689-704.
26. Spaventa, L. (1987). The growth of public debt: sustainability, fiscal rules, and monetary rules. *Staff papers*, 34(2), 374-399.
27. Tahir, P., & Ahmad, E. (1998). The Debt of the Nation [with Comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 331-353.
28. <https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx>
29. <https://www.imf.org/en/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/01/16/39/Debt-Sustainability-Framework-for-Low-Income-Countries>.